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District wise comparative study of GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 - Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

In this paper district wise comparative study of GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 was calculated and mapped. Study is based on secondary data collected from official website of Government of India. District wise GDP was classified in five categories based on Natural Breaks (Jenks) scheme. First with more than 15135.04 rupees crore, second with 10702.71 to 13173.22 rupees crore, third with 6114.761 to 8282.169 rupees crore, fourth with 3905.553 to 5754.828 rupees crore and fifth less than 3729.969 rupees crore. Result shows four districts belong to first category, eight districts belong to second category, twelve districts belong to third category, twenty two districts belong to fourth category and twenty two districts belong to fifth category.

Key words: GDP, Natural Breaks, Uttar Pradesh

1. Introduction

An IMF publication states that "GDP measures the monetary value of final goods and services - that is, those that are bought by the final user - produced in a country in a given period of time (say a quarter or a year)."[1]

The history of the concept of GDP should be distinguished from the history of changes in ways of estimating it. The value added by firms is relatively easy to calculate from their accounts, but the value added by the public sector, by financial industries, and by intangible asset creation is more complex. These activities are increasingly important in developed economies, and the international conventions governing their estimation and their inclusion or exclusion in GDP regularly change in an attempt to keep up with industrial advances. In the words of one academic economist "The actual number for GDP is therefore the product of a vast patchwork of statistics and a complicated set of processes carried out on the raw data to fit them to the conceptual framework." [2]

The Economy of India is the seventh-largest economy in the world measured by nominal GDP and the third-largest by purchasing power parity (PPP). [3]

Real GDP growth or Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of India at constant (2011-12) prices in the year 2015-16 is estimated at 7.56 percent as compared to the growth rate of 7.24 percent in 2014-15. Quarterly GDP growth rates are : Q1 (7.5%), Q2 (7.6%), Q3 (7.2%), Q4 (7.9%). [4]

Uttar Pradesh's gross state domestic product for 2004 is \$339.5 billion by PPP and \$80.9 billion by nominal and in 2013-14 it was 130 billion dollars by nominal which is the second highest in India. [5]

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

Uttar Pradesh, with a total area of 243,290 square kilometres, is India's fourth largest state in terms of land area. It is situated on the northern spout of India and shares an international boundary with Nepal. The Himalayas border the state on the north but the plains that cover most of the state are distinctly different from those high mountains. The larger Gangetic Plain region is in the north; it includes the Ganges-Yamuna Doab, the Ghaghra plains, the Ganges plains and the Terai. The smaller Vindhya Range and plateau region is in the south. [6]

2.2. Materials

Data: Secondary data collected from official website of government of India.

Software: ArcGIS 10.1, Excel

2.3 Methodology

Study is based on secondary data collected from official website of Government of India. District wise GDP was classified in five categories based on Natural Breaks (Jenks) scheme. First with more than 15135.04 rupees crore, second with 10702.71 to 13173.22 rupees crore, third with

6114.761 to 8282.169 rupees crore, fourth with 3905.553 to 5754.828 rupees crore and fifth less than 3729.969 rupees crore.

3. Result

Result shows four districts belong to first category (Table 1), eight districts belong to second category (Table 2), twelve districts belong to third category (Table 3), twenty two districts belong to fourth (Table 4) category and twenty two districts belong to fifth category (Table 5).

Table 1 GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 - UP

SN	Districts	GDP - Rs. Cr.
1	Lucknow	16954.58
2	Kanpur Dehat	16636
3	Ghaziabad	15602.18
4	GBN	15135.04

Source : <https://data.gov.in>

Table 2 GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 – U.P.

SN	Districts	GDP - Rs. Cr.
1	Allahabad	13173.22
2	Agra	12316.32
3	Meerut	12213.73
4	Muzaffarnagar	11933.19
5	Moradabad	11409.99
6	Bulandshahr	10780.14
7	Bareilly	10767.6
8	Bijnor	10702.71
9	Saharanpur	10237.3
10	Aligarh	9439.325

Source : <https://data.gov.in>

Table 3 GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 - Uttar Pradesh

SN	Districts	GDP - Rs. Cr.
1	Sitapur	8282.169
2	Badaun	8094.708
3	Lakhimpur Kheri	7952.115
4	Gorakhpur	7878.748
5	Mathura	7500.224
6	Varanasi	7127.113
7	Bara Banki	6897.135

8	Shahjahanpur	6343.591
9	Hardoi	6340.133
10	Jhansi	6322.863
11	Unnao	6134.773
12	Azamgarh	6114.761

Source : <https://data.gov.in>**Table 4 GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 - UP**

SN	Districts	GDP - Rs. Cr.
1	Jaunpur	5754.828
2	Pilibhit	5459.154
3	Firozabad	5397.643
4	Sonbhadra	5319.7
5	Sultanpur	5295.929
6	JP Nagar	5276.083
7	Ghazipur	5250.233
8	Rampur	5170.651
9	Etah	5048.213
10	Gonda	4757.668
11	Rae Bareli	4693.079
12	Fatehpur	4617.551
13	Ballia	4579.35
14	Baghpat	4568.229
15	Kushinagar	4520.014
16	Faizabad	4418.751
17	Hathras	4352.183
18	Bahraich	4099.265
19	Jalaun	4062.476
20	Pratapgarh	4034.063
21	Mirzapur	3968.409
22	Deoria	3905.553

Source : <https://data.gov.in>

Table 5 GDP based at current price (2004-05) from 2004-05 to 2011-12 – U.P.

SN	Districts	GDP - Rs. Cr.
1	Mau	3729.969
2	Farrukhabad	3727.8
3	Mainpuri	3681.489
4	Chandauli	3567.948
5	Ambedkar Nagar	3513.776
6	Kanpur	3512.103
7	Maharajganj	3467.981
8	Basti	3328.88
9	Banda	3276.745
10	Kannauj	3182.909
11	Siddharth Nagar	3167.318
12	Etawah	3133.265
13	Balrampur	3024.615
14	Auraiya	2906.301
15	Sant Ravi Das	2859.219
16	Kaushambi	2844.666
17	Lalitpur	2696.308
18	Hamirpur	2506.868
19	Mahoba	2169.518
20	Sant Kabir Nagar	2079.263
21	Chitrakoot	1609.735
22	Shravasti	1561.809

Source : <https://data.gov.in>

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